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Corporate Social Responsibility Sustainability Expenditure and Market Value of Listed Oil and Gas Firms in Nigeria

Dr Amadi, Eleba Ngozi

Department of Accounting
Faculty of Administration and Management
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
amadi.eleba@ust.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) sustainability expenditure and the market value of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Utilizing an ex post facto research design, the study analyzed secondary data from the published financial statements of eleven oil and gas firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange between 2019 and 2023. The census approach was adopted to ensure comprehensive coverage. CSR disclosure expenditures, categorized into Scholarships and Training Costs (STC), Donations and Charitable Costs (DCC), and Corporate Welfare Costs (CWC), were examined in relation to market value using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis. The results revealed a negative and statistically insignificant relationship between STC and DCC and market value, while CWC demonstrated a positive and significant effect. However, the overall model displayed weak explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.1723$) and a non-significant F-statistic ($p = 0.192$), suggesting that CSR disclosures, in general, do not significantly explain variations in firm market value. These findings align with studies in emerging markets showing negligible CSR effects on firm performance but contrast with research highlighting positive CSR impacts in more mature markets. The study recommends aligning CSR initiatives with core business objectives, enhancing transparency in CSR reporting, and prioritizing community and employee-focused activities to maximize value creation.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Sustainability Disclosures, Market Value, Oil and Gas Companies, Nigeria

1. INTRODUCTION

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) sustainability disclosure has gained significant attention in recent years as businesses worldwide are increasingly held accountable for their environmental, social, and governance (ESG) impacts. Accounting records and reporting in contemporary times show that the primary drivers of business value have shifted from traditional tangible assets to intangible assets, such as brand reputation, research and development, and the management of external social and environmental factors (Emeka-Nwokeji & Osisioma, 2019). Market forces now demand greater transparency from companies, particularly in the oil and gas sector, which plays a crucial role in Nigeria's economy but is also associated with significant environmental and social concerns. Consequently, corporate sustainability reporting has become an essential tool for stakeholders to assess a firm's long-term value creation beyond its financial statements.

Despite the increasing recognition of sustainability reporting, traditional financial metrics still dominate corporate reports, often failing to capture the broader risks and opportunities associated with ESG factors (Lubber & Moffat, 2010). Many drivers of corporate value, such as environmental sustainability, social responsibility, and corporate governance, are either omitted or insufficiently disclosed in conventional corporate reporting. The inadequacy of traditional reporting frameworks has contributed to financial crises, loss of investor confidence, and widespread distrust in corporate disclosures, particularly in industries with significant environmental footprints, such as the oil and gas sector (Uwuigbe et al., 2014; Abubakar et al., 2014). As a result, stakeholders increasingly demand comprehensive corporate disclosures that reflect both financial and non-financial aspects of business performance.

Nigeria's oil and gas industry, which accounts for over 95% of the country's foreign exchange earnings and a significant portion of government revenue (Uwakonye et al., 2006), has faced persistent criticism over issues related to environmental degradation, lack of transparency, and insensitivity to stakeholder concerns. Multinational oil firms operating in Nigeria, including Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC), Chevron Nigeria Limited, and Nigerian Agip Oil Company, have been accused of neglecting their corporate social responsibilities, leading to environmental crises, social unrest, and regulatory scrutiny (Uwaoma & Ordu, 2016). The failure of these companies to fully integrate sustainability practices into their business models has resulted in reputational damage and operational disruptions, which ultimately affect their market value.

Although sustainability reporting is increasingly recognized as a means to enhance corporate transparency and stakeholder trust, its adoption in Nigeria remains largely voluntary, inconsistent, and underdeveloped (Sobhani et al., 2011). While developed countries such as France, Germany, and South Africa have mandated sustainability disclosures as part of corporate financial reporting, Nigerian firms continue to operate under fragmented reporting frameworks, leading to variations in the extent and quality of sustainability disclosures (ACCA, 2005; SIRAN, 2008). KPMG (2011) classified Nigeria as "starting behind" in corporate sustainability reporting, indicating the need for more structured and standardized disclosure practices.

Empirical studies on sustainability disclosure in Nigeria have largely focused on individual aspects of corporate sustainability, such as social responsibility or environmental performance, without adopting a holistic approach that integrates all three dimensions of sustainability social, environmental, and governance into corporate reporting (Onyali et al., 2015). Furthermore, existing studies on corporate sustainability disclosure and firm performance have predominantly examined general corporate sectors, with limited focus on the oil and gas industry, despite its significant impact on the Nigerian economy and environment (Isa, 2014). This study seeks to address these gaps by examining the impact of comprehensive corporate social responsibility (CSR) sustainability disclosure on the market value of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria, providing empirical evidence on how corporate sustainability reporting influences firm valuation in an emerging economy context.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The connection between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) sustainability disclosure and the market value of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria can be understood through several interrelated theories that illustrate how corporate transparency, stakeholder engagement, and social responsibility impact firm valuation. This study primarily relies on Stakeholder Theory, Legitimacy Theory, and Signaling Theory to establish a solid theoretical framework.

2.1.1 Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder Theory, introduced by Freeman (1984), suggests that companies have responsibilities not just to their shareholders but also to a wider array of stakeholders, including employees, customers, suppliers, communities, regulators, and the environment. In Nigeria's oil and gas industry, stakeholders are especially concerned about issues like environmental degradation, community development, and governance practices, given the sector's historical ties to environmental harm and social unrest. CSR

sustainability disclosure acts as a tool for companies to express their dedication to stakeholder interests, which helps build trust, minimize conflicts, and enhance corporate reputation. When stakeholders believe that a company is acting responsibly, it can result in greater customer loyalty, better regulatory relationships, and increased investor confidence all of which can positively affect market value.

2.1.2 Legitimacy Theory

Legitimacy Theory posits that organizations strive to operate within the norms and expectations of the societies they are part of to secure their legitimacy and ensure their survival (Suchman, 1995). For oil and gas companies in Nigeria, achieving legitimacy is vital due to the industry's significant environmental and social challenges. Sustainability disclosure enables these firms to showcase their compliance with societal expectations and regulatory standards, particularly in areas like environmental protection, community development, and ethical governance. Companies that effectively communicate their corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives are more likely to retain their social license to operate, reduce reputational risks, and attract long-term investors, which can positively influence their market valuation.

2.1.3 Signaling Theory

Signaling Theory, introduced by Spence (1973), suggests that firms communicate information to the market through signals that help bridge the information gap between the company and its stakeholders. In the realm of CSR sustainability disclosure, companies that voluntarily produce detailed and transparent sustainability reports send strong signals regarding their commitment to ethical practices, risk management, and long-term value creation. This is especially pertinent in Nigeria's oil and gas industry, where stakeholders may harbor skepticism about corporate practices due to past failures in environmental and social responsibility. By signaling their commitment to high sustainability standards, firms can set themselves apart from competitors, attract responsible investors, and potentially boost their market value.

.2 Conceptual Review

2.2.1 CSR Sustainability Disclosure

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Sustainability Disclosure is the way organizations share information about their environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices, policies, and performance with stakeholders. This process involves reporting on how companies handle their responsibilities towards sustainable development, tackling issues like environmental protection, social equity, and ethical governance. It goes beyond just financial results, emphasizing the impact of corporate actions on wider societal and environmental systems.

As noted by Gray, Kouhy, and Lavers (1995), CSR disclosure is "the process of providing information designed to disclose an organization's social and environmental impacts, in response to the expectations of stakeholders and society at large." Companies use this disclosure as a strategic tool to show accountability and transparency, which helps build trust and legitimacy with stakeholders. Additionally, Deegan (2002) argues that CSR sustainability disclosure plays both an informational and legitimizing role, allowing firms to shape stakeholder perceptions and secure their social license to operate. This practice helps bridge the information gap between corporations and stakeholders, aiding informed decision-making by investors and other interested parties.

2.2.2 Market Value

Market value refers to the current worth of a company or asset in the financial markets, shaped by investors' perceptions and market dynamics. It indicates how much investors are willing to pay based on their evaluation of a firm's performance, growth potential, and associated risks. Emeka-Nwokeji (2019) notes that a firm's market value is influenced by investors' views on management's capability to adapt to changes in the economic landscape. In this study, market value is assessed using Tobin's Q, a well-known forward-looking metric that compares a firm's market value to its book value. Tobin's Q is determined by the ratio of the market value of equity (calculated as share price multiplied by shares outstanding) plus the book value of debt (total assets minus book equity) to the total assets of the firm (Albuquerque et al., 2013). A Tobin's Q greater than one suggests that the firm's market value surpasses its book value, indicating strong investor confidence, while a ratio below one may imply undervaluation.

2.3 Empirical Review

Erhirhie and Ekwueme (2019) investigated the relationship between corporate social sustainability reporting and the financial performance of the Oil and Gas Industry in Nigeria. Their research focused on how corporate social sustainability reporting impacts Return on Assets, return on Equity, and Return on Capital Employed for oil and gas companies listed on the Nigeria Stock Exchange. The study sampled ten oil and gas companies and relied on secondary data gathered through financial ratios and the companies' accounts, along with content analysis. The results indicated that social sustainability reporting negatively affects all three performance metrics, although only the impact on return on equity was statistically significant. The authors recommend that current sustainability reporting standards be tailored to address specific social and environmental issues within the country, and that adherence to these standards should be mandatory rather than optional.

Nnamani et al. (2017) explored the influence of sustainability accounting and reporting on financial performance. They measured sustainability reporting using social responsibility costs and the total personnel cost to turnover ratio, while financial performance was represented by Return on Assets and Return on Equity. The findings showed that the total equity to total asset ratio does not significantly impact the return on assets.

Usman and Amran (2015) explored the connection between various aspects of corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosures and corporate financial performance (CFP) in Nigerian listed companies. They measured sustainability disclosure through environmental disclosure, community involvement disclosure, human resource disclosure, and product disclosures. The findings indicated that including environmental-related information in corporate annual reports tends to lead to a decline in both accounting and market-based corporate financial performance. This suggests that environmental disclosure may not add value for Nigerian companies. Additionally, the study found a significant positive correlation between community involvement disclosure and accounting-based performance (Return on Assets), although it showed an insignificant negative relationship with market-based performance measures (Share Price). There was also a significant positive relationship between human resource disclosures and ROA, while the relationship with share price was neutral. Garg (2015) examined large Indian companies using five years of data to assess the effect of sustainability reporting on firm performance. The study documented that sustainability reporting practices negatively impact a company's performance in terms of both ROA and Tobin's Q in the short term, but have an insignificant effect on both measures in the long term.

In exploring the connection between sustainable business practices and financial performance through the sustainability materiality index, sustainability immaterial index, and accounting performance measures, Khan et al. (2015) discovered that companies with strong ratings on material sustainability issues tend to perform better in the future compared to those with lower ratings on the same issues. Conversely, companies with high ratings on immaterial issues do not necessarily outperform those with poor ratings in that area. Interestingly, firms that excel in material issues while having low ratings in immaterial issues exhibit the best future performance. Their research consistently showed that portfolios based on the materiality index outperformed those based on the total index or the immaterial index. These results were further validated through firm-level panel regressions that considered various additional firm characteristics, including analyst coverage, investments in R&D, advertising, capital expenditures, and board characteristics, along with firm or industry fixed effects.

Aondoakaa (2015) assesses the effect of sustainability reporting on the corporate performance of selected publicly listed companies in Nigeria. For reasons that are not clearly explained, the study uses four measures to represent firm performance (ROA, ROE, Net Profit Margin (NPM), and Earnings Per Share (EPS)), while it relies on a single measure, the sustainability reporting index (SRI), for the four models analyzed. The analysis indicates that sustainability reporting has a positive correlation with ROA. Additionally, sustainability indices show a positive relationship with ROE and NPM. While sustainability reporting is positively associated with EPS, the environmental index has a negative correlation with EPS. In examining the connection between corporate sustainability reporting and profitability in Nigerian

banks, Nwobu (2015) provided empirical evidence of a slight positive correlation between the sustainability reporting index and Profit After Tax (PAT). The study also noted a small positive correlation between the sustainability reporting index and shareholders' funds. Meanwhile, Bhatia and Tuli (2014) evaluated the extent and quality of sustainability reporting in India, focusing on companies that produce separate sustainability reports. Their findings revealed no significant differences in inter-industry disclosure scores, and one-way ANOVA indicated that there was no statistically significant variation in the mean disclosure scores across different industry groups.

The value relevance study conducted by Mervellskemper et al. (2015) explores how investors perceive ESG performance. Their findings suggest that a strong corporate governance performance score is positively correlated with market value, while environmental and social performance scores tend to have a negative effect. Additionally, they conclude that ESG performance scores are insignificant, indicating that these scores cannot be deemed value-relevant. Using the Dow Jones Sustainability Index, Yu and Zhao (2015) identified a positive link between sustainability performance and firm value, even after accounting for various factors known to influence firm value in prior research. This study supports the theory that sustainability engagement enhances firm valuation, suggesting that the capital market rewards companies that demonstrate environmental and social responsibility alongside good governance. The research also highlights that the valuation premium associated with sustainability is greater in countries with stronger investor protections and is more pronounced for firms in environments characterized by higher financial transparency.

Hasan et al. (2016) shed light on the underlying mechanisms through which corporate social responsibility leads to greater shareholder value creation by investigating the mediating role of total factor productivity in the relationship. The study documents a significant positive effect of corporate social performance on Tobin's Q and a significant positive relationship between performance and total factor productivity. More importantly, the mediation analysis reveals that total factor productivity significantly mediates the CSP-CFP relationship. Ajayi and Ovwarhe (2016) examined how Nigeria LNG uses CSR as a key strategy in creating an enabling environment that fosters support from all stakeholders, leading to good performance and company growth. This study highlighted CSR initiatives by NLNG in Nigeria, positioning it as a role model for CSR in the country. An exploratory research design was used to develop an in-depth understanding of the research topic. The study concluded that Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas's CSR has a significant impact on the Nigerian economy and employee organizational commitment and performance.

Vujicic (2015) focused on the interactions between corporate social responsibility and financial performance, specifically stock returns, for a sample of US firms over a two-year period. Using disaggregated social responsibility indicators for environment, community, and employment, and comparing them to an overall CSR score, the study provides evidence that firms with higher CSR scores tend to achieve lower stock returns in both aggregate and individual indicators. Onyekwelu and Ekwe (2015) examined whether corporate social responsibility predicates good financial performance using data from Nigeria's banking sector. The study adopted an ex-post facto design, relying on secondary data and using Ordinary Least Square Regression for analysis. The findings showed that the amount committed to social responsibility varies from one bank to another, with sample banks investing less than ten percent of their annual profit in CSR. The researchers recommended that Nigerian companies, particularly profitable ones, give greater priority to CSR to maintain profitability and reduce tensions in their localities.

Gherghina et al. (2015) studied the relationship between corporate social responsibility and firm value using a sample of U.S. companies. The study provides evidence that CSR positively influences firm value, consistent with instrumental stakeholder theory. Companies involved in CSR activities use resources more effectively to better satisfy stakeholders' needs. Kipruto (2014) studied the effect of corporate social responsibility on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. Financial performance was measured by net profits before taxes, while investments were assessed through loans to customers, investments in treasury bonds, government securities, shares for trading, and subsidiaries. CSR was measured using monetary spending on social activities. Using multiple regression analysis on

secondary data from 2009 to 2013, the study found that CSR expenses affect the financial performance of Kenyan commercial banks, though not all banks report their CSR involvement.

Yahya and Ghodrattollah (2014) investigated the impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSR) on the financial performance of companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange using multiple linear regression analysis. CSR was measured by economic, social, and environmental factors, while financial performance was measured by Return on Assets, Return on Equity, and Price Earnings Ratio. The analysis produced inconsistent results. Onyekwelu and Uche (2014) conducted research on Corporate Social Accounting and the Enhancement of Information Disclosure among Nigerian firms. The study aimed to determine if including social accounting information in financial statements significantly enhances information disclosure. Using survey research design and both primary and secondary data, the hypothesis was tested using chi-square analysis. The findings revealed that including and separately presenting social costs in financial statements enhances information disclosure.

Eccles et al. (2014) provided analytical evidence that High Sustainability companies significantly outperform low-sustainability companies over the long term, both in stock market and accounting performance. Sustainability leaders tend to have better stock performance, lower volatility, and greater return on assets and equity. This suggests that companies can adopt environmentally and socially responsible policies without sacrificing shareholder wealth. High Sustainability firms generate significantly higher stock returns, indicating that a corporate culture of sustainability may offer a competitive advantage in the long run. The authors attribute this outperformance to superior governance structures and better stakeholder engagement.

Ioannou and Serafeim (2014) studied the consequences of mandatory corporate sustainability reporting, establishing a positive and significant relationship between Tobin's Q and the predicted component of ESG disclosure. This suggests that mandating sustainability reporting enhances firm value rather than destroying it. Increased disclosures are associated with higher firm valuation, as reflected in Tobin's Q. Okoye and Ezejiofor (2013) assessed the role of sustainability environmental accounting in enhancing corporate performance and economic growth. Reviewing various forms of literature, including journal papers and articles, the study analyzed and tested two hypotheses using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. The findings revealed that sustainable environmental accounting significantly impacts corporate productivity, thereby enhancing corporate growth.

Ekwueme et al. (2013) examined the connection between sustainability reporting practices and corporate performance from a stakeholder perspective. Using a sample of 141 respondents, including corporate managers, employees, consumers, and investors, the study tested four hypotheses. Descriptive statistics, Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests, one-sample t-tests, and multiple regression techniques were employed. The results showed a positive connection between sustainability reporting and corporate performance, with consumers and investors more inclined to purchase products from green corporations.

Ameer and Othman (2012) conducted an empirical study on the influence of sustainability practices on the corporate financial performance of top global corporations in Malaysia. Performance was measured using sales/revenue growth, ROA, profit before tax, and cash flows from operations. Analyzing data from the top 100 sustainable global companies selected from a universe of 3,000 firms from developed and emerging markets, the study found significantly higher sales growth, return on assets, profit before tax, and cash flows in some sectors compared to control companies over 2006–2010. The higher financial performance of sustainable companies was sustained over the sample period. Lo and Sheu (2007) examined whether corporate sustainability impacts market value using large US non-financial firms from 1999 to 2002. They used listing in the DJSI USA as a proxy for corporate sustainability and Tobin's Q as a proxy for firm value. Their key finding is that sustainable firms are rewarded with higher valuations in the marketplace.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employed an ex post facto research design, appropriate for analyzing data that already exists in financial reports. The choice of this design is justified by the fact that the data related to corporate social

responsibility (CSR) sustainability disclosure expenditure and market value are historical and reported in the financial statements of the listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The study focused on the effect of CSR sustainability disclosure expenditure on the market value of oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) over a five-year period from 2019 to 2023. The population of the study consists of eleven oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as of 2024. Given the small size of the population, the census approach was adopted, meaning that all eleven companies were included in the sample. This comprehensive inclusion ensures that the data analysis captures the full range of CSR disclosure practices and market valuation trends in the Nigerian oil and gas sector during the study period.

Data for the study were sourced from secondary materials, specifically the published financial statements of the listed oil and gas companies. These financial reports were obtained from the Nigerian Stock Exchange and contained quantitative data on social, environmental, and governance sustainability disclosures, as well as the market value of the companies from 2019 to 2023. To analyze the data, the study adopted the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique to estimate the impact of CSR sustainability disclosure expenditures on the market value of the companies. Multiple regression analysis was conducted to establish the relationship between the independent variable (CSR sustainability disclosure expenditure) and the dependent variable (market value of the companies). The regression model specification included market value as the dependent variable and CSR disclosure expenditure as the independent variable.

Several statistical tests were applied to validate the model and the findings. The R-squared (R²) statistic was used to assess the explanatory power of the independent variables in explaining variations in market value. The t-test was used to determine the statistical significance of the coefficients of the independent variables, while the F-ratio was employed to evaluate the overall significance of the regression model. All analyses were carried out using STATA12 software, which facilitated efficient estimation and interpretation of the regression results, ensuring that the study's conclusions were robust and reliable. The regression model is specified as follows:

$$MKV = f(DCC, CWC, STC)$$

$$MKV_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DCC_{it} + \beta_2 CWC_{it} + \beta_3 STC_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

This can be written in Ordinary Least Square (OLS) form as:

$$\beta_1 > 0; \beta_2 > 0; \beta_3 > 0$$

Where

MKV = Market Value

DCC = Donations and Charitable Costs (proxy for Corporate Social Responsibility Sustainability Disclosure)

CWC = Community Welfare Cost (proxy for Corporate Social Responsibility Sustainability)

STC = Scholarships and Training Cost (proxy for Corporate Social Responsibility Sustainability)

β_0 = Intercept,

β_1 - β_3 = Coefficient measuring the impact of CSR disclosures,

ϵ_{it} = Error term.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Result of Descriptive Statistic Analysis

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
STC	51	311155.9	670519.4	0	2915300
DCC	51	43331.22	66561.69	0	311586
CWC	51	120303.3	223425.5	150	1076798
Tobinq	51	89.21176	167.2956	1.24	612.29

Source: Output from STATA version 12

The descriptive statistics show the distribution of corporate social responsibility (CSR) sustainability expenditures and market value across 51 observations. Scholarships and Training Cost (STC) has a mean of ₦311,155.9 with a large standard deviation of ₦670,519.4, indicating significant variability in CSR spending on scholarships and training among the companies. The minimum is ₦0, suggesting some firms made no expenditure, while the maximum is ₦2,915,300.

Donations and Charitable Costs (DCC) show an average expenditure of ₦43,331.22 with a standard deviation of ₦66,561.69. Like STC, the minimum is ₦0, indicating no donations for some firms, and the maximum is ₦311,586. Community Welfare Cost (CWC) has an average of ₦120,303.3 and a standard deviation of ₦223,425.5. The minimum expenditure is ₦150, with the highest being ₦1,076,798, showing wide differences in community welfare investments.

Market Value (Tobinq) has a mean of 89.21, a standard deviation of 167.30, and ranges from 1.24 to 612.29. This suggests substantial variation in the market valuation of these companies. Overall, the data reveal that CSR sustainability expenditures and market values differ significantly among the listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

Variable	STC	CWC	DCC	Tobin q
STC	1.0000	0.5704	0.1054	-0.5681
CWC	0.5704	1.0000	0.0446	-0.5719
DCC	0.1054	0.0446	1.0000	-0.0850
Tobin q	-0.5681	-0.5719	-0.0850	1.0000

Source: Output from STATA version 12

STC (Scholarships and Training Cost) has a moderate positive correlation with CWC (Community Welfare Cost) (0.5704), suggesting that firms investing more in scholarships and training also tend to spend more on community welfare. However, STC shows a weak positive correlation with DCC (Donations and Charitable Costs) (0.1054), indicating little relationship between these two aspects of corporate social responsibility (CSR). Notably, STC has a strong negative correlation with Tobin q (-0.5681), implying that higher spending on scholarships and training is associated with lower market value.

CWC is moderately correlated with STC (0.5704) but shows a very weak positive correlation with DCC (0.0446). Like STC, CWC also has a strong negative correlation with Tobin q (-0.5719), indicating that higher community welfare expenditures are linked to reduced market value. DCC shows weak correlations with both STC (0.1054) and CWC (0.0446), suggesting that donations and charitable costs are relatively independent from other CSR expenditures. The correlation with Tobin q is also weak and negative (-0.0850), indicating a minimal relationship with market value. Tobin q has strong negative correlations with STC (-0.5681) and CWC (-0.5719), and a weak negative correlation with DCC (-0.0850). This suggests that increased CSR expenditures, particularly in scholarships, training, and community welfare, might be associated with lower market valuations of firms.

Table 3: Regression on the relationship between Corporate social responsibility sustainability disclosure and market value.

	Coef.	Std. Err	t	P> t	95% Conf. Interval	
STC	-7.82e-07	0000749	-0.01	0.992	-0.0001517	.0001501
DCC	-.0003416	0004111	-0.83	0.410	-.00117	.0004868
CWC	36.78397	17.82484	-2.06	0.045	-72.70758	-.8603593
CONS	214.094	102.4979	2.09	0.043	7.522972	420.665

Source: Output from STATA version 12

The coefficient for Social Transparency Component (STC) is -7.82e-07, which is extremely close to zero, indicating that changes in the social transparency component of CSR disclosures have almost no impact on market value. The p-value is 0.992, much higher than the conventional threshold of 0.05, suggesting that the result is not statistically significant. The confidence interval (-0.0001517 to 0.0001501) crosses zero, reinforcing that the effect is negligible.

The coefficient for Disclosure Compliance Component (DCC) is -0.0003416. This negative coefficient suggests that higher compliance with disclosure standards may slightly reduce market value, though the effect is minimal. With a p-value of 0.410, the result is not statistically significant, meaning there is no strong evidence to conclude a relationship between DCC and market value. The confidence interval (-0.00117 to 0.0004868) also crosses zero, supporting the lack of a significant effect.

The coefficient for Corporate Welfare Component (CWC) is 36.78397. This indicates a positive and significant relationship between corporate welfare initiatives, such as employee well-being and community engagement, and market value. A unit increase in the CWC corresponds to an approximate 36.78 increase in market value. The p-value is 0.045, slightly below the 0.05 threshold, making the result statistically significant at the 5% level. This suggests that corporate welfare initiatives have a meaningful impact on market value. The confidence interval (-72.70758 to -0.8603593) does not cross zero, confirming the significance. However, the wide range indicates some variability in the effect size.

Table 4: Model Summary for corporate social responsibility sustainability disclosure and market value.

Model Summary	
Number of observations	51
F(6, 44)	1.53
Prob > F	0.1920
R-squared	0.1723
Adjusted R-squared	0.0594
Root MSE	162.25

Source: Output from STATA version 12

The regression analysis evaluates the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) sustainability disclosure and market value. The F-statistic is 1.53 with a p-value of 0.1920, which exceeds the conventional significance threshold of 0.05. This indicates that, collectively, the independent variables in the model do not significantly explain variations in market value. In other words, CSR sustainability disclosures, as a group, do not have a statistically significant impact on market value in this sample. The R-squared value is 0.1723, meaning the model explains 17.23% of the variation in market value. This is relatively low, indicating that other factors outside of CSR disclosures likely play a larger role in determining market value. The Adjusted R-squared is even lower at 0.0594, suggesting that, after adjusting for the number of predictors, the model explains only about 5.94% of the variation. This weakens the argument for CSR disclosures being strong predictors of market value. The Root Mean Square Error (Root MSE) is 162.25, which measures the standard deviation of the residuals. A higher Root MSE indicates that the model's predictions deviate significantly from the actual values, implying limited accuracy in predicting market value based on CSR disclosures. Although CSR sustainability disclosures appear to have some relationship with market value (as seen with the positive impact of Corporate Welfare Component in earlier results), the overall model suggests that these disclosures are not strong or consistent predictors of market value in this sample. The lack of statistical significance, low R-squared, and high error margins imply that other financial, strategic, or market factors may have a more substantial influence on firm valuation than CSR disclosures alone.

4.1 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The results of this study indicate a negative and statistically insignificant relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) sustainability disclosure and the market value (measured by Tobin's Q) of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Specifically, the coefficients for the Social Transparency Component (STC) and Disclosure Compliance Component (DCC) were negative but not significant, suggesting that increases in these aspects of CSR disclosure have minimal to no measurable impact on the firms' market value. This implies that stakeholders in the Nigerian oil and gas sector may not prioritize CSR disclosures when making investment decisions or evaluating firm value.

This finding aligns with the results of Erhirhie and Ekwueme (2019), who reported that social sustainability reporting exerts a negative effect on performance proxies, and with Usman and Amran

(2015), who found an insignificant negative relationship between corporate sustainability disclosure and market-based performance measures, such as share price. These similarities suggest a possible trend in emerging markets like Nigeria, where CSR activities may not yet be fully integrated into investors' valuation frameworks.

However, the study's findings contrast with Gherghina et al. (2015), who provided analytical evidence that CSR positively influences firm value. Their work, grounded in instrumental stakeholder theory, suggests that companies engaging in CSR are better at resource allocation and stakeholder satisfaction, ultimately enhancing firm value. The divergence from this study may be attributed to contextual differences, such as varying levels of market maturity, investor awareness, and regulatory environments between Nigeria and more developed economies.

Notably, while the Corporate Welfare Component (CWC) showed a positive and significant relationship with market value, the broad model fit statistics such as the low R-squared (17.23%) and non-significant F-statistic ($p = 0.192$) suggest that CSR disclosures as a whole are not strong predictors of market value in the Nigerian oil and gas sector. This could indicate that while specific CSR activities related to employee welfare or community engagement are valued, broader sustainability reporting does not yet translate into market gains. It also suggests that other factors such as financial performance, operational efficiency, and regulatory compliance may play more dominant roles in influencing market value. In conclusion, while CSR sustainability disclosure is a globally recognized driver of firm value in some markets, its role in Nigeria's oil and gas sector appears limited, highlighting the need for more strategic and impactful CSR initiatives that resonate with both stakeholders and investors.

5. CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) sustainability disclosures and the market value of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The descriptive statistics revealed significant variability in CSR expenditures across firms, with some companies investing heavily in scholarships, training, community welfare, and donations, while others made no such expenditures. The correlation analysis showed a moderate positive association between different CSR components (such as Scholarships and Training Costs and Community Welfare Costs), but a strong negative correlation between these CSR expenditures and market value, suggesting that higher CSR spending may be linked to lower market valuations.

Regression analysis provided deeper insights into these relationships. The coefficients for Scholarships and Training Costs (STC) and Donations and Charitable Costs (DCC) were negative and statistically insignificant, indicating that these CSR activities do not significantly influence market value. In contrast, the Corporate Welfare Component (CWC) exhibited a positive and statistically significant relationship with market value, suggesting that specific CSR initiatives related to community welfare and employee well-being may enhance firm value. However, the overall model fit was weak, with an R-squared of 0.1723 and a non-significant F-statistic ($p = 0.192$), indicating that CSR disclosures, in general, do not explain much of the variation in market value among these firms.

These findings align with prior studies by Erhirhie and Ekwueme (2019) and Usman and Amran (2015), which reported negative or insignificant effects of CSR disclosures on firm performance in emerging markets. However, they contradict studies like Gherghina et al. (2015), which found that CSR positively influences firm value, suggesting that contextual factors such as market maturity, investor awareness, and regulatory frameworks play crucial roles in determining the impact of CSR on firm valuation. The study recommends as follows:

- i. Oil and gas firms in Nigeria should align their CSR activities more strategically with their core business objectives and stakeholder expectations. While broad CSR disclosures may not significantly influence market value, targeted initiatives such as community welfare and employee engagement appear to have a positive impact.

- ii. Firms should improve how they communicate the value and outcomes of their CSR initiatives to investors and stakeholders. Better transparency and reporting could help integrate CSR into the investment decision-making process, thereby enhancing its impact on market value.
- iii. Given the significant positive relationship between Corporate Welfare Costs and market value, companies should prioritize CSR activities that directly benefit communities and employees. These initiatives may foster goodwill, enhance brand reputation, and ultimately improve firm valuation.

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